

Sequential activation of σ -bonds : Intermolecular cascade annulation with migration and remote functionalization[†]

Dipankar Dhara^a, Tista Sengupta^a, Saikat Khamarui^a, Sukla Ghosh^{b*} and Dilip K. Maiti^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, University College of Science,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : dkmchem@caluniv.ac.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Gobardanga Hindu College, Gobardanga-743 273, West Bengal, India

E-mail : maitisuklaghc@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 18 July 2013, accepted 20 July 2013

Abstract : We demonstrate a new catalytic property of the lanthanide compound $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ which sequentially activates N-H, sp^2 C-H and sp^3 C-H σ -bonds at ambient temperature. The powerful catalyst enables selective C-C and C-N bond-forming intermolecular cascade annulation between enamines and diaryl-1,2-diketone to afford functionalized 3,3-diaryl-3-pyrrolin-2-ones involving migration of an aromatic ring. We have also initiated a new multicomponent strategy utilizing readily available and inexpensive precursors and environmentally benign $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as an efficient catalyst under benign reaction conditions towards direct synthesis of several N-heterocycles including pentasubstituted 2-pyrrolinones and pyrroles. These observations provide new prospects and perspectives in σ -bond activation process for easy access to functional molecules.

Keywords : Sequential activation of σ -bonds, $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, cascade annulation, migration, remote functionalization, pentasubstituted 2-pyrrolinones and pyrroles.

Introduction

Last three decades have observed the spectacular progress of transition metal-catalyzed σ -bond activation, functionalization and cyclization in synthetic chemistry towards production of functional molecules with excellent reaction convergence, yield and selectivities¹. However, there are only a few examples using lanthanide compounds for this purpose². Conventional C-C coupling requires substrates bearing a reactive C-X bond which generates large amount of halogen waste. Since the 1960s, the synthetic research professionals of industrial and academic settings are investigating for development of the cheapest and cleanest protocols for synthesis of organic molecules and metal-mediated direct C-H activation was found as the most economic ways for C-C bond formation. The "activation" of a Y-H or C-Y (Y = C, N, etc.) σ -bond means enhancement of its reactivity towards a reagent due to its internal manipulation with some external force exerted by metals, which leads to relatively

weakening or cleavage of the bond. This process introduce new bond, functionality and can efficiently be utilized for many fundamental organic transformations. Mechanistically, breaking of a σ -bond occurs due to two synergic transfers of electron density of the metal complex (ML_n) involving bonding σ -donation of molecular orbital (MO) into a vacant one and simultaneous π -back donation from an occupied MO into the antibonding orbital which subsequently ruptures the σ -bond.

However, major disadvantage of this C-H activation approach is requirement of a directing and/or chelating group(s) and the installed group should be removed or can be a permanent part of the end product. Most of the methodologies need stoichiometric amount of metal salts as a supporting catalyst and also stringent reaction conditions, which has restricted substrate scope, enhances overhead cost and environmental hazards. However, it still offers new concept, innovative chemistry and scope for solving many unsolved and new challenges in organic

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

synthesis. For instance, selective activation of sp^2 C-H and sp^3 C-H is a very difficult job for the chemists. However, it can be done by sequential activation which will be initiated through ease incorporation of metal into the relatively weak bond like N-H σ -bond of a precursor. In the following proposed Scheme 1, enamine (4) bearing N-H, vinylic sp^2 C-H and allylic sp^3 C-H σ -bonds can be activated with a metal in a sequential fashion. Insertion of metal to the relatively weaker N-H bond (I) is a facile process which undergoes activation of sp^2 C-H (II) through its migration. The intermediate II proceeds for C-C coupling with an aromatic 1,2-diketone (3) along with shifting of metal to activate the neighbour sp^3 C-H (III). Thus, the sequential σ -bond activation process would lead to C-N bond-forming cascade cyclization³ to intermediate IV involving the same catalyst. It will provide easy access to several ubiquitous *N*-heterocycles through 1,2-shift of aromatic ring or remote functionalization.

ture drug candidates for pharmaceutical industries and as a nanobuilding block in fabrication of organic opto-electronic devices⁴. Recent research in medicinal chemistry demonstrated that pyrrolinones are useful drug candidates such as selective inhibitors of monopyrrolinone-based HIV-1 protease, VEGF R2/3, HIV-1 integrase, HIF-2 and phosphodiesterase, nucleic acid aptamer, antimalarial symprostatin 4 and pyrrolinone oligomer-based gallinamide A, *N*-aryl-3-alkylidenepyrrolinones as a niemann-pick type C disease therapeutics and pyrrolinone-based peptidomimetics⁵. The 2-pyrrolinone analogues like a patented drug (A, Fig. 1) as phosphodiesterase inhibitor, metalloprotease inhibitor (B) and tetrapetalone A (C) alkaloid displaying significant soybean lipoxygenase (SBL) inhibitory activity may be cited in this context⁶. Polysubstituted pyrrole-containing natural products are extremely abundant in nature such as haemoglobin, chlorophylls, vitamin B₁₂, lukianols and tetrapentalones and found widespread applications as pharmaceuticals

Scheme 1. Proposed route for sequentially activated cyclization.

Fig. 1. Pyrrolinone-based bioactive natural products.

2-Pyrrolinones and their analogues are an attractive class of *N*-heterocycles due to their stability, availability as an important skeleton in several natural products, fu-

(e.g. Lipitor), agrochemicals, flavor additives, organoleptics, synthetic building blocks and materials for molecular sensors and high-tech devices⁷. In addition,

most of the pyrrole skeleton-containing alkaloids are highly substituted and have additional rings fused to the pyrrole conferring a higher degree of molecular complexity.

We are particularly interested towards direct synthesis of a new series of 3,3-diaryl-3-pyrrolin-2-one compounds from commercially available inexpensive precursors and reagent for development of their antimalarial and antituberculosis activity⁸ under our OSDD (open source drug discovery) program⁹ and potential use as a highly sensitive high-tech nanodevices¹⁰ under our DST-Nanomission project. Other than our recently published strategy, synthesis of the pentasubstituted 3,3-dialkyl-3-pyrrolin-2-one and side-chain-functionalized pyrroles are not investigated^{2b}. However, tremendous application of the pyrrole compounds led to the development of transition metal-catalyzed more efficient cyclization methods which are encouraging. The most frequently used approaches for synthesis of pyrrolinones and pyrroles are the classical Hantzsch, Knorr and Paal-Knorr, cycloaddition and multistep processes^{11,12}. The substrate scope of the newer methods is very limited due to use of acidic or basic reaction conditions, predesigned precursors, stoichiometric amount of unsafe metals as a copromotor and/or high temperature. Thus, it remains highly desirable to develop methods requiring milder conditions as well as avoiding the need for toxic metal catalysts. We demonstrated recently about the role of cerium(III) compounds in cascade cyclization^{2b,10a}. In a continuous effort to synthesize ubiquitous heterocycles from readily available and inexpensive precursors¹³, we disclose herein the sequential activation of N-H and C-H σ -bonds utilizing rare-earth metal compound under neutral and benign reaction conditions, which leads to C-C and C-N bond forming

cascade cyclization and subsequent migration of substituents and remote functionalization towards easy access to highly substituted ubiquitous *N*-heterocycles.

Results and discussion

The easy access of a wide variety of such multifunctionalized *N*-heterocycles from common starting materials and reagents is possible through development of an efficient intermolecular domino approach¹⁴ where all chemical transformations will be executed in a single operation using same catalyst under similar reaction conditions. In our initial experiments, we synthesized the enamine (**4a**) from methyl acetoacetate (**1a**) and benzyl amine (**2a**) using cerium(III) chloride as a catalyst (3 mol%) in tetrahydrofuran (THF) at ambient temperature (Scheme 2). Sequential activation of N-H, vinylic sp^2 C-H and allylic sp^3 C-H σ -bonds of **4a** towards domino cascade cyclization with diaryl-1,2-diketone (benzil : **3a**) was attempted using several trivalent lanthanide compounds (5 mol%) such as La(OTf)₃, Eu(OTf)₃, Tb(OTf)₃, Ho(OTf)₃, Tm(OTf)₃, Yb(OTf)₃ and others. Unfortunately, the metal-catalyzed intermolecular domino strategy was unsuccessful to construct the desired *N*-heterocycle (**5a**) even under heating conditions. However, treatment of the enamine (**4a**) with 5 mol% of the CeCl₃·7H₂O afforded the desired product **5a** (entry 1, Table 1) along with remote-functionalized pentasubstituted pyrroles **6a** with moderate yield (61%). However, the one-pot synthesis was developed using 7 mol% of the catalyst which first generated the enamine (**4a**) from the 3-keto ester (**1**) and aliphatic amine (**2**) and subsequently coupled with diaryl-1,2-diketone through sequential activation of the N-H, vinylic sp^2 C-H and allylic sp^3 C-H σ -bonds and cascade cyclization to construct the desired products (**5a** and **6a**).

Scheme 2. Development of cascade annulation approach.

We have developed the domino reaction at ambient temperature by direct C–C and C–N bond-forming cascade cyclization involving a sequential activation of N–H, vinylic sp^2 C–H and allylic sp^3 C–H of enaminoesters on use of acetylene-equivalent 1,2-diketone and water tolerable rare-earth metal catalyst $CeCl_3 \cdot 7H_2O$. Functional

group decorated pentasubstituted 3,3-diaryl-3-pyrrolin-2-ones (**5a-j**) and pyrroles (**6a-j**) were synthesized with high yield (78–92%) under the neutral and benign reaction conditions (Table 1). The novel *N*-heterocycles were separated by simple column chromatography (silica gel) using ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (60–80) as an eluent. It is

Table 1. Experimental data of sequential N–H and C–H activated cyclization reaction

Entry	3-Ketoester (1)	Amine (2)	1,2-Diketone (3)	Time (h)	2-Pyrrolinone (5)	Pyrrole (6)	Product ratio (5 : 6)	Yield (%)
1.		23 : 22	90					
2.		48 : 43	91					
3.	1a		54 : 31	85				
4.	1b	2b	3a	24		62 : 23	85	
5.		46 : 35	81					
6.	1a		37 : 2	78				
7.	1c	2b	3a	29		2 : 79	81	
8.	1b		1 : 87	88				
9.	1b		1 : 91	92				
10.	1b	2a		54 : 37	91			

interesting to observe that placement of large group as a substituent of aliphatic amine ($R^3 = \text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{CMe}_3$) led to exclusive formation of 2-pyrrolinone (**5f**; entry 6) where as the equilibrium was completely shifted toward construction of pentasubstituted pyrrole (**6g,h**; entries 7–9) when steric and electronic factor was drastically reduced ($R^3 = \text{Me}$; **6h**) or enhanced ($R^1 = \text{CMe}_3$; **6g**). However, it was surprising to us when we found exclusively pentasubstituted pyrrole **6i** (entry 9) from the post reaction mixture. The structures of all the new compounds (**5** and **6**) were characterized by spectroscopic and single crystal X-ray diffraction analyses¹⁵ (Fig. 2).

desired 2-pyrrolinone (**5**, Scheme 3, *path-a*). On the other hand, intermediate **VI** reacted with a second molecule of the β -ketoester (**3**) at the side-chain to produce the penta-substituted pyrroles (**6**, Scheme 3, *path-b*).

In contrast to the diaryl-1,2-diketone (**3a,b**, Table 1), on use of diacetyl (**3c** : $R^4 = \text{Me}$) migration of R^4 was completely restricted and it produced correspondingly remotely functionalized pentasubstituted pyrrole (**7**, Scheme 4) as a sole product through nucleophilic addition of **1b** to the intermediate **VI** with excellent yield (84%). However, utilizing 1,2-cyclohexadione [**3d** : $R^4-R^4 = (\text{CH}_2)_4$] corresponding spiro-2-pyrrolinone (**8a,b**) were obtained

Fig. 2. Single crystal XRD structure of **5b** and **6i**.

Scheme 3. Possible mechanistic path of the cascade cyclization.

The three-component assembly of cyclization is believed to proceed through formation of intermediate **V** and 1,2-shift of an aryl group (from C-1 to C-2) by the influence of the powerful catalyst, which afforded the

involving rearrangement of cyclic alkyl chain in intermediate **V**. These experimental observations indicated the selectivity of the powerful cerium(III) with varied substrate and also the steric and electronic factors appearing

Scheme 4. Substrate tuned synthesis of various *N*-heterocycles.

in the transition state, which led to the formation of the several heterocyclic scaffolds. On use of aromatic amine (2), a competition between nucleophilic 3-ketoester (1) and aromatic amine (2) was observed and it afforded dimirized compound 10 with nice architecture and the remote-functionalized product 9. Yield of compound 10 was improved to 71% when 4-chloroaniline was used for N-C coupling with the intermediate VI. Formation of intermediate VI was also confirmed when we used $R^1 = Et$, and corresponding elimination product (11) was observed with complete *trans*-selectivity.

Conclusion

We have demonstrated that lanthanide metal salt $CeCl_3 \cdot 7H_2O$ is a keen catalyst for sequential activation of σ -bonds. It has shown outstanding catalytic power for the selective C-C and C-N bond-forming cascade cyclization with migration of aromatic ring and remote functionalization to afford several nitrogen-containing ubiquitous architectures. We anticipate that this new concept in catalysis will find considerable application in synthetic organic chemistry, medicinal chemistry and material sciences through innovative catalyst design using inexpensive and green rare-earth metal compounds, easy synthesis of such a diverse class of highly functionalized pentasubstituted 2-pyrrolinones and pyrroles and their valuable applications.

Experimental

General procedure for synthesis of compound 5 and 6: β -Keto ester (1, 1.25 mmol), aliphatic amine (2, 1.25 mmol), $CeCl_3 \cdot 7H_2O$ (100 mg, 5 mol %), KI (100 mg, 15 mol %) and anhydrous $MgSO_4$ were taken in dry THF (30 mL) and stirred for 24 h at room temperature. Benzil (3a, 1 mmol) was added to it and stirred at room temperature to complete the domino reaction. The reaction was monitored by TLC. After evaporation of the solvent, the post reaction mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (25 mL). This organic layer was washed with water (3 \times 10 mL) and dried on anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The solvent was removed under reduced pressure in a rotary evaporator at room temperature. The residue was then subjected to column chromatography over silica gel (60–120 mesh) and eluted with ethyl acetate in petroleum ether (v/v) to afford corresponding pentasubstituted 2-pyrrolinone (5) and pyrrole (6).

Characterization data :

1-Benzyl-4-methoxycarbonyl-5-methyl-3,3-diphenyl-2-pyrrolinone (5a): Yield 46%; colourless crystalline solid; m.p. 86–88 °C; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 2.50 (3H, s), 3.54 (3H, s), 4.83 (2H, s), 7.03–7.05 (5H, m), 7.25–7.34 (10H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 13.20, 43.83, 50.55, 63.64, 113.36, 126.85, 127.28, 127.78, 127.94, 128.91, 128.96, 136.45, 139.95, 154.27, 164.28, 179.86; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 608.0, 696.1, 747.5,

937.4, 984.6, 1061.7, 1125.8, 1214.0, 1343.4, 1387.5, 1441.6, 1492.5, 1617.8, 1692.0, 1721.7, 1888.6, 1959.1, 2281.0, 2375.9, 2854.2, 2943.1, 3028.9, 3422.8, 3754.1, 3906.2; HR-MS (m/z) for $C_{26}H_{24}NO_3$ (M+H) calcd. 398.1756, found 398.1751.

1-Benzyl-2-(2-methoxycarbonyl-3-oxobutyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid methyl ester (6a) : Yield 44%; yellow liquid; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 2.23 (3H, s), 3.20–3.36 (2H, dd, J 14.8 and 7.15 Hz), 3.54 (3H, s), 3.65 (3H, s), 4.24–4.29 (1H, t, J 6.4 Hz), 5.12–5.30 (2H, dd, J 17.4 and 34.5 Hz), 6.77–6.79 (2H, m), 6.80–6.95 (2H, m), 7.03–7.20 (8H, m), 7.21–7.25 (3H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 24.35, 29.92, 47.69, 50.50, 52.41, 58.90, 111.69, 124.48, 125.41, 125.75, 126.94, 127.14, 127.69, 127.92, 128.69, 128.92, 130.67, 131.21, 131.39, 132.88, 135.47, 136.59, 138.13, 165.81, 169.82, 203.13; FTIR (neat, cm^{-1}) : 700.9, 732.7, 842.1, 1031.3, 1149.1, 1200.3, 1239.3, 1401.5, 1513.5, 1605.4, 1695.9, 1957.1, 2953.7, 3133.5; HR-MS (m/z) for $C_{31}H_{30}NO_5$ (M+H) calcd. 496.2124, found 496.2131.

1-Benzyl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-5-methyl-3,3-diphenyl-2-pyrrolinone (5b) : Yield 48%; colourless crystalline solid; m.p. 122–123 °C; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 0.92 (3H, dt, J 7.1 and 1.19 Hz), 2.43 (3H, s), 3.92 (2H, dq, J 7.1 and 1.2 Hz), 4.75 (2H, s), 7.07–7.09 (3H, m), 7.17–7.24 (12H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 13.11, 13.92, 43.82, 59.51, 63.58, 113.52, 126.88, 127.25, 127.76, 127.85, 128.90, 129.07, 136.53, 139.98, 154.21, 163.92, 179.93; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 698.5, 731.1, 844.9, 888.2, 943.7, 1064.3, 1133.9, 1215.9, 1298.5, 1333.3, 1391.6, 1450.4, 1493.8, 1623.8, 1685.4, 1725.5, 1881.8, 1956.9, 2372.3, 2976.0, 3030.6, 3429.4, 3699.7, 3753.9, 3856.4; HR-MS (m/z) for $C_{27}H_{26}NO_3$ (M+H) calcd. 412.1913, found 412.1909.

1-Benzyl-2-(2-ethoxycarbonyl-3-oxobutyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (6b) : Yield 43%; yellow liquid; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 0.91 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.18 (3H, t, J 6.9 Hz), 2.22 (3H, s), 3.17–3.33 (2H, m), 3.97–4.02 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 4.06–4.13 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 4.26–4.31 (1H, t, J 8.0 Hz), 5.07–5.28 (2H, dd, J 7.1 and 4.4 Hz), 6.76–6.78 (2H, d, J 6.7 Hz), 6.89–6.92 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 7.02–7.03 (8H, m), 7.05–7.23 (3H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 13.71, 14.04, 24.33, 29.97, 47.71, 59.07, 59.41, 61.45, 112.00, 124.58, 125.48, 125.74, 126.94, 127.16, 127.68,

127.94, 128.73, 130.82, 131.22, 131.48, 132.71, 135.77, 136.52, 138.22, 165.48, 169.49, 203.35; FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}) : 704.9, 730.6, 857.2, 914.5, 1036.3, 1097.3, 1158.4, 1241.9, 1295.5, 1368.1, 1412.6, 1449.2, 1514.1, 1605.7, 1712.0, 1885.6, 1955.5, 2253.9, 2335.9, 2981.3, 3032.6, 3058.8, 3421.8, 3643.0, 4055.5, 4338.2; HR-MS (m/z) for $C_{33}H_{34}NO_5$ (M+H) calcd. 524.2437, found 524.2438.

1-Ethoxycarbonylmethyl-4-methoxycarbonyl-5-methyl-3,3-diphenyl-2-pyrrolinone (5c) : Yield 54%; colourless crystalline solid; m.p. 76–78 °C; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.22 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 2.45 (3H, s), 3.45 (3H, s), 4.14–4.21 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 4.28 (3H, s), 7.16–7.28 (10H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 12.61, 14.05, 41.56, 50.58, 62.08, 63.49, 113.58, 127.27, 127.86, 129.01, 139.72, 152.99, 164.20, 167.74, 179.66; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 700.9, 748.5, 842.9, 883.7, 948.8, 1018.7, 1079.4, 1128.3, 1204.0, 1343.7, 1373.3, 1446.5, 1493.0, 1626.9, 1690.5, 1736.5, 1959.5, 2373.7, 2958.4, 2996.8, 3448.6, 3622.5, 3689.9, 3754.2, 3906.3; HR-MS (m/z) for $C_{23}H_{24}NO_5$ (M+H) calcd. 394.1654, found 394.1663.

1-Ethoxycarbonylmethyl-2-(2-methoxycarbonyl-3-oxobutyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid methyl ester (6c) : Yield 31%; yellow liquid; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.11–1.20 (3H, m), 2.22 (3H, s), 3.19–3.26 (1H, dd, J 1.5 and 7.5 Hz), 3.31–3.38 (1H, dd, J 1.5 and 6.0 Hz), 3.49 (3H, s), 3.69 (3H, s), 4.04–4.11 (2H, q, J 6.9 Hz), 4.32–4.38 (1H, t, J 6.9 Hz), 4.64 (1H, d, J 18.3 Hz), 4.71 (1H, d, J 18.3 Hz), 6.95–7.18 (10H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 13.95, 24.16, 30.06, 46.15, 50.44, 52.48, 58.83, 61.50, 111.57, 124.23, 125.71, 126.84, 127.92, 128.10, 130.56, 131.17, 132.46, 135.25, 137.08, 165.66, 168.80, 169.82, 203.29; FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}) : 699.3, 1203.4, 1447.9, 1515.5, 1703.4, 2369.6, 2946.0, 3438.5, 3754.0; HR-MS (m/z) for $C_{28}H_{29}NO_7$ (M+H) calcd. 491.1944, found 491.1938.

Mixture of 1-ethoxycarbonylmethyl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-5-methyl-3,3-diphenyl-2-pyrrolinone (5d) and 1-ethoxycarbonylmethyl-2-(2-ethoxycarbonyl-3-oxobutyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (6d) : Total yield 85% (**5d** : **6d** = 62 : 23); yellow liquid; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 0.93–1.04 (9H, m), 1.21–1.33 (9H, m), 1.57 (2H, s), 2.36 (3H, s), 2.55 (3H, s), 3.24–3.47 (2H, dd, J 7.2 and 14.8 Hz), 4.00–4.07 (4H, m), 4.17–

4.27 (9H, m), 4.45 (1H, t, J 6.9 Hz), 4.73–4.84 (2H, dd, J 18.2 and 50.3 Hz), 7.04–7.11 (10H, m), 7.22–7.36 (10H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 13.91, 14.02, 24.17, 30.18, 46.23, 59.03, 59.33, 59.58, 61.58, 112.01, 118.14, 125.73, 126.88, 127.27, 127.80, 127.94, 128.17, 129.15, 130.77, 131.25, 132.37, 135.64, 137.02, 162.32, 165.37, 168.93, 169.46; FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}): 855.50, 946.96, 1071.28, 1096.89, 1175.90, 1206.23, 1296.22, 1373.35, 1445.83, 1520.11, 1608.67, 1626.53, 1693.84, 1714.44, 1747.36, 2981.95, 2936.90, 3059.34.

1-Benzyl-4-tert-butylloxycarbonyl-5-methyl-3,3-diphenyl-2-pyrrolinone (5e): Yield 46%; colourless crystalline solid; m.p. 104 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.14 (9H, s), 2.43 (3H, s), 4.74 (2H, s), 7.08–7.26 (15H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 12.89, 28.07, 43.79, 80.42, 126.95, 127.19, 127.73, 127.77, 128.89, 129.13, 136.73, 139.89, 153.50, 163.45, 179.97; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 692.6, 736.3, 768.9, 836.2, 948.2, 1060.0, 1130.5, 1173.6, 1223.7, 1301.9, 1342.9, 1375.9, 1448.3, 1490.2, 1630.7, 1681.4, 1709.6, 1952.5, 2293.5, 2931.0, 2971.6, 3025.8, 3387.2; HR-MS (m/z) for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{30}\text{NO}_3$ ($M+H$) calcd. 440.2226, found 440.2220.

1-Benzyl-2-(2-tert-butoxycarbonyl-3-oxobutyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid t-butyl ester (6e): Yield 35%; colourless liquid; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.20 (9H, s), 1.36 (9H, s), 2.19 (3H, s), 3.11–3.19 (1H, dd, J 15.0 and 8.7 Hz), 3.25–3.32 (1H, dd, J 15.0 and 8.7 Hz), 4.18–4.23 (1H, t, J 1.5 Hz), 5.01–5.25 (2H, dd, J 17.4 and 55.2 Hz), 6.79–7.26 (18H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 24.02, 27.88, 27.95, 28.08, 29.64, 47.67, 59.94, 79.44, 81.75, 113.85, 124.45, 125.56, 125.67, 127.05, 127.11, 127.56, 127.78, 127.91, 128.69, 129.14, 130.79, 131.26, 131.75, 132.20, 135.77, 136.41, 138.31, 165.01, 168.91, 203.45; FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}): 697.8, 846.5, 1033.6, 1146.3, 1248.9, 1304.0, 1365.3, 1450.9, 1515.7, 1607.2, 1687.1, 1721.3, 1956.3, 2361.5, 2931.8, 2976.5, 3423.5, 3690.1, 3754.2, 3906.0; HR-MS (m/z) for $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{42}\text{NO}_5$ ($M+H$) calcd. 580.3063, found 580.3069.

1-tert-Butoxycarbonylmethyl-4-methoxycarbonyl-5-methyl-3,3-diphenyl-2-pyrrolinone (5f): Yield 74%; colourless crystalline solid; m.p. 144 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.49 (9H, s), 2.53 (3H, s), 3.53 (3H, s), 4.27 (2H, s), 7.24–7.36 (10H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75

MHz, CDCl_3): δ 12.67, 28.00, 42.42, 50.54, 83.18, 127.25, 127.87, 129.09, 139.89, 153.28, 164.30, 166.78, 179.60; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 696.0, 837.8, 877.6, 950.5, 1153.4, 1231.7, 1361.2, 1446.5, 1623.8, 1689.3, 1734.6, 1955.4, 2376.6, 2984.9, 3438.8, 3751.2, 3854.1; HR-MS (m/z) for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{28}\text{NO}_5$ ($M+H$) calcd. 422.1967, found 422.1976.

1-Ethoxycarbonylmethyl-2-(2-tert-butoxycarbonyl-3-oxobutyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid tert-butyl ester (6g): Yield 79%; yellow liquid; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.22–1.27 (12H, m), 1.42 (9H, s), 2.31 (3H, s), 3.17–3.25 (1H, dd, J 4.5 and 8.1 Hz), 3.34–3.41 (1H, dd, J 6.3 and 14.7 Hz), 4.12–4.19 (2H, q, J 14.1 Hz), 4.31–4.35 (1H, t, J 6.9 Hz), 4.61 (1H, d, J 18.3 Hz), 4.83 (1H, d, J 18.3 Hz), 7.03–7.26 (10H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 14.09, 23.80, 27.85, 27.90, 29.68, 30.01, 46.15, 59.87, 61.53, 79.37, 81.93, 113.77, 124.25, 125.56, 127.00, 127.84, 128.13, 130.72, 131.23, 131.52, 131.86, 136.19, 136.31, 164.80, 168.86, 169.00, 203.86; FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}): 760.76, 788.40, 844.42, 920.77, 1098.73, 1149.65, 1248.60, 1302.14, 1392.07, 1450.09, 1477.70, 1523.75, 1562.93, 1604.12, 1686.49, 1736.15, 2930.66, 2978.51, 3059.91; HR-MS (m/z) for $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{42}\text{NO}_7$ ($M+H$) calcd. 576.2961, found 576.2967.

1-Methyl-2-(2-ethoxycarbonyl-3-oxobutyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (6h): Yield 87%; yellow liquid; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 0.98–1.07 (3H, m), 1.26–1.31 (3H, m), 2.35 (3H, s), 2.65 (1H, s), 3.19 (1H, s), 3.50–3.55 (3H, s), 4.06–4.13 (2H, m), 4.19–4.26 (2H, m), 4.40–4.50 (1H, t, J 6.0 Hz), 7.12–7.15 (5H, m), 7.27–7.30 (5H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 13.78, 14.09, 24.40, 30.12, 32.28, 58.76, 59.33, 61.52, 111.38, 124.12, 125.75, 126.99, 127.24, 127.57, 127.83, 128.09, 129.09, 130.86, 131.26, 131.73, 132.49, 135.91, 136.38, 162.33, 165.52, 169.47, 203.43; FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}): 703.0, 769.1, 855.3, 920.7, 1054.0, 1157.9, 1225.9, 1283.7, 1368.3, 1449.9, 1514.9, 1609.2, 1692.2, 1889.5, 1953.7, 2340.2, 2981.0, 3055.2, 3427.8; HR-MS (m/z) for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{30}\text{NO}_5$ ($M+H$) calcd. 448.2124, found 448.2132.

2-(2-Ethoxycarbonyl-3-oxo-butyl)-1-methoxycarbonylmethyl-4,5-diphenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (6i): Yield 91%; colourless crystalline solid;

m.p. 122–124 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 0.94 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.25 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 2.35 (3H, s), 3.22–3.30 (1H, m), 3.36–3.43 (1H, m), 3.70 (3H, s), 4.01–4.08 (2H, m), 4.14–4.22 (2H, m), 4.41–4.46 (1H, m), 4.80 (2H, dd, J 50.4 and 18.3 Hz), 7.04–7.10 (6H, m), 7.21–7.25 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 13.7, 14.0, 24.1, 30.2, 46.0, 52.5, 59.0, 59.3, 61.6, 112.0, 124.4, 125.7, 126.9, 128.0, 128.2, 130.7, 131.2, 132.4, 135.5, 137.0, 165.3, 169.4, 169.4, 203.6; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 701, 974, 1155, 1217, 1519, 1685, 1745, 2373, 2982, 3065; HR-MS (m/z) for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{31}\text{NO}_7$ (M) calcd. 505.2101, found 505.2102.

1-Benzyl-4,4-bis-(4-bromophenyl)-2-methyl-5-oxo-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (5j) : Yield 54%; colourless crystalline solid; m.p. 102–104 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.06 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 2.52 (3H, s), 4.02 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 4.82 (2H, s), 7.14–7.17 (6H, m), 7.28–7.34 (3H, m), 7.41–7.45 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 13.2, 14.0, 43.9, 59.8, 62.7, 112.6, 121.7, 126.9, 126.9, 128.0, 128.9, 129.0, 130.6, 130.7, 130.8, 131.1, 131.3, 136.2, 138.7, 154.8, 163.4, 179.0; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 785, 938, 1059, 1134, 1295, 1389, 1488, 1695, 1716, 2984, 3063; HR-MS (m/z) for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{23}\text{Br}_2\text{NO}_3$ (M) calcd. 567.0045, found 567.0040 (one of the peaks).

1-Benzyl-4,5-bis-(4-bromophenyl)-2-(2-ethoxycarbonyl-3-oxobutyl)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (6j) : Yield 37%; colourless solid; m.p. 128–130 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 0.50 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.26 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 2.31 (3H, s), 3.28–3.36 (2H, m), 4.08–4.22 (4H, m), 4.32–4.37 (1H, m), 5.25 (2H, dd, J 45.6, 17.4 Hz), 6.83 (4H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 6.97–7.00 (2H, m), 7.25–7.32 (7H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 13.4, 13.6, 23.8, 29.5, 47.4, 58.6, 59.2, 61.1, 111.6, 119.7, 121.9, 123.4, 124.9, 127.0, 128.5, 129.7, 129.9, 131.0, 131.1, 132.1, 132.2, 134.1, 136.9, 137.4, 164.7, 168.9, 202.6; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 694, 720, 827, 1011, 1151, 1244, 1297, 1415, 1520, 1683, 1714, 2934, 2982, 3794; HR-MS (m/z) for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{33}\text{Br}_2\text{NO}_5$ (M+2) calcd. 681.0569, found 681.0566 (one of the peaks).

1-Benzyl-2-(2-ethoxycarbonyl-3-oxobutyl)-4,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (7) : Yield 84%; yellow liquid; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.13 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.28 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.92 (3H, s), 2.12 (3H, s), 2.15 (3H, s), 3.13–3.28 (2H, s), 3.99–4.25 (5H,

m), 5.16 (2H, dd, J 37.5 and 17.7 Hz), 6.73 (2H, d, 6.6 Hz), 7.14–7.23 (3H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 9.7, 11.5, 13.9, 14.4, 24.0, 30.0, 46.7, 59.1, 59.2, 61.3, 111.2, 116.6, 125.4, 125.7, 127.1, 128.7, 135.4, 137.7, 166.0, 169.3, 203.5; FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}) : 731, 1030, 1116, 1230, 1271, 1399, 1440, 1512, 1692, 1720, 2397, 2981, 3128; HR-MS (m/z) for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{29}\text{NO}_5$ (M) calcd. 399.2046, found 399.2044.

2-(1-Cyclohexylethyl)-3-methyl-1-oxo-2-aza-spiro[4.4]non-3-ene-4-carboxylic acid tert-butyl ester (8a) : Yield 84%; colourless crystalline solid; m.p. 99–101 °C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 0.66–0.79 (3H, m), 0.95–1.21 (4H, m), 1.26 (3H, s), 1.39 (3H, s), 1.43 (6H, s), 1.64–1.68 (6H, m), 1.78–2.08 (7H, m), 2.23 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 25.7, 25.8, 26.1, 27.1, 28.5, 30.9, 35.6, 54.6, 113.7, 152.9, 163.9, 185.1; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 973, 1052, 1086, 1173, 1388, 1454, 1611, 1685, 1716, 2665, 2853, 2930, 2973, 3395; HR-MS (m/z) for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{35}\text{NO}_3$ (M) calcd. 361.2617, found 361.2612.

2-(1-Cyclohexylethyl)-3-methyl-1-oxo-2-aza-spiro[4.4]non-3-ene-4-carboxylic acid methyl ester (8b) : Yield 81%; yellow liquid; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 0.71–0.84 (2H, m), 1.20–1.25 (4H, m), 1.29 (3H, m), 1.35 (3H, m), 1.60–1.63 (4H, m), 1.71–1.75 (4H, m), 1.83–2.00 (6H, m), 3.69 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 25.7, 25.8, 26.1, 27.3, 30.9, 35.9, 50.5, 54.4, 112.5, 153.9, 164.8, 185.1; FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}) : 773, 1019, 1070, 1210, 1259, 1141, 1615, 1694, 2251, 2668, 2853, 2929, 3400; HR-MS (m/z) for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{29}\text{NO}_3$ (M) calcd. 319.2147, found 319.2142.

Phenylamino-bis[(2-methyl)-14,5-triphenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (10a) : Yield 53%; yellow liquid; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 0.78 (6H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 4.04 (4H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 4.31 (4H, s), 6.38 (3H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 6.59 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz), 6.73–6.79 (4H, m), 6.86–7.03 (10H, m), 7.09–7.36 (16H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 13.8, 39.3, 59.7, 113.7, 117.7, 124.4, 126.0, 126.8, 127.1, 127.4, 127.8, 128.3, 128.6, 128.9, 129.0, 131.0, 131.1, 132.6, 135.3, 137.0, 137.2, 147.9, 165.5; FT-IR (neat, cm^{-1}) : 751, 871, 915, 1077, 1183, 1249, 1286, 1369, 1444, 1499, 1601, 1689, 2979, 3053, 3383; HR-MS (m/z) for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{49}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$ (M) calcd. 851.3723, found 851.3720.

4'-Chlorophenylamino-bis[(2-methyl)-4,5-diphenyl-1-(4-chlorophenyl)-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (10b) : Yield 71%; colourless crystalline solid; m.p. 120–122 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.06 (6H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 4.14–4.21 (4H, m), 4.39–4.55 (4H, m), 6.47 (4H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 6.87–6.90 (4H, m), 7.05–7.25 (12H, m), 7.32–7.36 (12H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 13.8, 39.5, 59.9, 114.2, 114.8, 122.6, 124.7, 126.2, 127.1, 127.2, 127.7, 128.9, 129.2, 129.8, 130.7, 130.9, 131.0, 132.7, 134.4, 135.0, 135.7, 136.4, 146.3, 165.4; FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 827, 1047, 1169, 1281, 1498, 1618, 1715, 2928, 3365; HR-MS (*m/z*) for C₅₈H₄₆Cl₃N₃O₄ (M) calcd. 953.2554, found 953.2550.

3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-(2-ethoxycarbonyl-3-oxobutyl)-4,5-diphenyl-cyclopenta-1,4-dienecarboxylic acid ethyl ester (9b) : Yield 26%; yellow liquid; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 0.98 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 1.17 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 2.13 (3H, s), 2.17 (2H, s), 3.38–3.48 (2H, m), 4.00–4.11 (4H, m), 6.76–6.79 (2H, m), 6.99–7.08 (4H, m), 7.11–7.18 (4H, m), 7.26–7.31 (4H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 13.7, 13.9, 24.3, 29.0, 58.8, 59.6, 61.4, 113.0, 126.0, 126.9, 127.1, 127.6, 129.1, 130.5, 130.8, 131.0, 131.0, 132.7, 134.3, 135.4, 135.7, 136.4, 165.3, 169.0, 202.1; FT-IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 765, 1078, 1188, 1275, 1494, 1689, 1716, 1738, 2106, 2853, 2925, 3436; HR-MS (*m/z*) for C₃₂H₃₀ClNO₅ (M) calcd. 543.1813, found 543.1811 (one of the peaks).

1-(4-Methoxybenzyl)-4,5-diphenyl-2-propenyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (11) : Yield 78%; yellow liquid; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.01 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 1.73–1.76 (3H, m), 3.80 (3H, m), 4.10 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz), 5.05 (2H, s), 6.12 (1H, dd, *J* 16.2 and 6.6 Hz), 6.58 (1H, d, *J* 17.7 Hz), 6.73–6.82 (5H, m), 6.99–7.28 (9H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 13.7, 19.2, 22.6, 31.9, 48.0, 55.2, 59.5, 113.9, 120.0, 124.5, 125.6, 127.0, 127.3, 127.5, 127.9, 130.2, 130.5, 130.7, 131.2, 131.6, 132.0, 132.8, 135.4, 135.6, 158.6, 166.0; FTIR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 760, 967, 1039, 1151, 1303, 1513, 1613, 1693, 2853, 2924, 3434; HR-MS (*m/z*) for C₃₀H₂₉NO₃ (M) calcd. 451.2147, found 451.2144.

Acknowledgement

Financial support from DST (SR/S1/OC-5/2012), India, and CSIR (SRF), India is gratefully acknowledged. SG thanks UGC, India, for the MR Project (F.PSW-121/10-11).

References

- (a) V. Ritleng, C. Sirlin and M. Pfeffer, *Chem. Rev.*, 2002, **102**, 1731; (b) H. M. L. Davies and J. R. Manning, *Nature*, 2008, **451**, 417; (c) J. F. Hartwig, *Nature*, 2008, **455**, 314; (d) Y. Saima, S. Khamarui, K. S. Gayen, P. Pandit and D. K. Maiti, *Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **48**, 6601; (e) P. B. Arockiam, C. Bruneau and P. H. Dixneuf, *Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **112**, 5879.
- (a) W. J. Evans, J. M. Perotti and J. W. Ziller, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 3894; (b) D. Dhara, K. S. Gayen, S. Khamarui, P. Pandit, S. Ghosh and D. K. Maiti, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2012, **77**, 10441.
- (a) K. C. Nicolaou and J. S. Chen, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2009, **38**, 2993; (b) T. Sengupta, K. S. Gayen, P. Pandit and D. K. Maiti, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2012, **18**, 1905. (c) S. Zhu and D. W. C. MacMillan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 10815.
- (a) R. G. Linington, B. R. Clark, E. E. Trimble, A. Almanza, L.-D. Ureña, D. E. Kyle and W. H. Gerwick, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 2009, **72**, 14; (b) C. C. Cosner, J. T. Markiewicz, P. Bourbon, C. J. Mariani, O. Wiest, M. Rujoi, A. I. Rosenbaum, A. Y. Huang, F. R. Maxfield and P. Helquist, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **52**, 6494; (c) S. Lu, M. Drees, Y. Yao, D. Boudinet, H. Yan, H. Pan, J. Wang, Y. Li, H. Usta and A. Facchetti, *Macromolecules*, 2013, **46**, 3895.
- (a) E. J. Merino and K. M. Weeks, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **125**, 12370; (b) C. Peifer, R. Selig, K. Kinkel, D. Ott, F. Totzke, C. Schachtele, R. Heidenreich, M. Rocken, D. Schollmeyer and S. Laufer, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **51**, 3814; (c) T. Conroy, J. T. Guo, N. H. Hunt and R. J. Payne, *Org. Lett.*, 2010, **12**, 5576; (d) J.-H. Xie and Q.-L. Zhou, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2008, **41**, 581; (e) H. R. Bokesch, R. S. Gardella, D. C. Rabe, D. P. Bottaro, W. M. Linehan, J. B. McMahon and T. C. Mckee, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 2011, **59**, 1178; (f) A. Raghuraman, E. Ko, L. M. Perez, T. R. Ioeberger and K. Burgess, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 12350.
- (a) A. B. Smith, III, T. Nittoli, P. A. Sprengeler, J. J.-W. Duan, R.-Q. Liu and R. F. Hirschmann, *Org. Lett.*, 2000, **2**, 3809; (b) A. P. Marcus and R. Sarpong, *Org. Lett.*, 2010, **12**, 4560; (c) A. Ripka, G. Shapiro and R. Chesworth, US Patent 2010/0137317; *Chem. Abstr.*, 2009, **152**, 97491.
- (a) F. Bellina and R. Rossi, *Tetrahedron*, 2006, **62**, 7213; (b) A. P. Marcus and R. Sarpong, *Org. Lett.*, 2010, **12**, 4560; (c) B. Pacorel, S. C. Leung, A. V. Stachulski, J. Davies, L. Vivas, H. Lander, S. A. Ward, M. Kaiser, R. Brun and P. M. O'Neill, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **53**, 633; (d) Z. Chen, X. Wang, W. Zhu, X. Cao, L. Tong, H. Li, H. Xie, Y. Xu, S. Tan, D. Kuang, J. Ding and X. Qian, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2011, **54**, 3732; (e) Y. Arikawa, H. Nishida, O. Kurasawa, A. Hasuoka, K. Hirase, N. Inatomi, Y. Hori, J. Matsukawa, A. Imanishi, M. Kondo, N. Tarui, T. Hamada, T. Takagi, T. Takeuchi and M. Kajino, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2012, **55**, 4446.
- (a) A. Zumla, R. Hafner, C. Lienhardt, M. Hoelscher and A. Nunn, *Nature Rev. Drug Discovery*, 2012, **11**, 171; (b)

- M. Peplow, *Nature*, 2013, **494**, 160.
9. OSDD: <http://www.osdd.net> (project no. OC_UCKLT 0001 & 0002; OSDD-CSIR, Govt. of India).
 10. (a) S. R. Forrest and M. E. Thompson, *Chem. Rev.*, 2007, **107**, 923; (b) P. Pandit, N. Chatterjee, S. Halder, S. K. Hota, A. Patra and D. K. Maiti, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2009, **74**, 2581; (c) D. K. Maiti, S. Halder, P. Pandit, N. Chatterjee, D. D. Joarder, N. Pramanik, Y. Saima, A. Patra and P. K. Maiti, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2009, **74**, 8086; (d) G. Hlawacek, F. S. Khokhar, R. V. Gastel, B. Poelsema and C. Teichert, *Nano Lett.*, 2011, **11**, 333; (e) K. Everaerts, J. D. Emery, D. Jariwala, H. J. Karmel, V. K. Sangwan, P. L. Prabhurashi, M. L. Geier, J. J. McMorrow, M. J. Bedzyk, A. Facchetti, M. C. Hersam and T. J. Marks, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2013, **135**, 8926.
 11. (a) A. R. Coffin, M. A. Roussel, E. Tserlin and E. T. Pelkey, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2006, **71**, 6678; (b) S. K. Dey and D. A. Lightner, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2008, **73**, 2704; (c) B. Ranieri, C. Curti, L. Battistini, A. Sartori, L. Pinna, G. Casiraghi and F. Zanardi, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2011, **76**, 10291; (d) A. Raghuraman, D. Xin, L. M. Perez and K. Burgess, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2013, **78**, 4823; (e) R. Spina, E. Colacino, B. Gabriele, G. Salerno, J. Martinez and F. Lamaty, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2013, **78**, 2698; (f) Z. Xu, F. D. Moliner, A. P. Cappelli and C. Hulme, *Org. Lett.*, 2013, **15**, 2738.
 12. (a) D. J. Gorin, N. R. Davis and F. D. Toste, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 11260; (b) J. T. Binder and S. F. Kirsch, *Org. Lett.*, 2006, **8**, 2151; (c) D. J. S. Cyr and B. A. Arndtsen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 12366; (d) Z. Zhang, J. Zhang, J. Tan and Z. Wang, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2008, **73**, 5180; (e) M. Lin, L. Hao, R.-d. Ma and Z.-p. Zhan, *Synlett.*, 2010, 2345; (f) V. Estévez, M. Villacampa and J. C. Menéndez, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2010, **39**, 4402; (g) S. Auricchio, A. M. Truscello, M. Lauria and S. V. Meille, *Tetrahedron*, 2012, **68**, 7441; (h) X. Xin, D. Wang, X. Li and B. Wan, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2012, **51**, 1693.
 13. (a) N. Chatterjee, P. Pandit, S. Halder, A. Patra and D. K. Maiti, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2008, **73**, 7775; (b) D. K. Maiti, N. Chatterjee, P. Pandit and S. K. Hota, *Chem. Commun.*, 2010, **46**, 2022; (c) D. K. Maiti, P. Pandit and N. Chatterjee, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 1285; (d) P. Pandit, K. S. Gayen, S. Khamarui, N. Chatterjee and D. K. Maiti, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 6933; (e) S. Khamarui, D. Sarkar, P. Pandit and D. K. Maiti, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 12667.
 14. (a) L. F. Tietze, G. Brasche and K. Gericke, "Domino Reactions in Organic Synthesis", Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, Germany, 2006; (b) M. Marigo, T. Schulte, J. Frazén and K. A. Jørgensen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 15710; (c) E. Fillion and D. Fishlock, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 13144; (d) K. S. Gayen, T. Sengupta, Y. Saima, A. Das, D. K. Maiti and A. Mitra, *Green Chem.*, 2012, **14**, 1589.
 15. CCDC number of **5b** : 885597 and **6i** : 950554.

